

A cross-sectional study of nurses' perspectives on the leadership styles of nursing managers

Farnaz Kiani ¹, Atefeh Boostanbakhsh ², Sima Vadaei ³, Razie Beigi Rizi ⁴, Mehrvash Hoseinpour ⁵, Naser Farahmandmoghadam ^{6,7,*}

1 Kermanshah University of Medical sciences, Kermanshah, Iran.

2 Department of Clinical Care Nursing, Farshchian Cardiovascular Hospital, Hamedan, Iran.

3 Psychiatric Nursing, Department of Nursing, Golpayegan Branch, Islamic Azad University, Golpayegan, Isfahan, Iran.

4 Geriatric Nursing, Mohammad Rasoul Allah Hospital, Mobareke, Isfahan, Iran.

5 Pediatric Nursing, University of Nursing & Midwifery, Tehran Medical Science Islamic Azad University, Tehran, Iran.

6 Clinical Research Development Center, Imam Khomeini, Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences, Kermanshah, Iran

7 Mohammad Kermanshahi Hospital, Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences, Kermanshah, Iran.

*. **Corresponding author:** Naser Farahmandmoghadam, Clinical Research Development Center, Imam Khomeini and Mohammad Kermanshahi Hospitals, Kermanshah University of Medical Sciences, Kermanshah, Iran. Phone: +98 912364512. Email: naserfarahmandmoghadam@gmail.com.

Cite this article: Kiani, F., Boostanbakhsh, A., Vadaei, S., Beigi Rizi, R., Hoseinpour, M., Farahmandmoghadam, N. A cross-sectional study of nurses' perspectives on the leadership styles of nursing managers. Int J Epidemiol Health Sci 2025;6: e86. Doi: [10.51757/IJEHS.6.2025.718627](https://doi.org/10.51757/IJEHS.6.2025.718627).

Abstract

Background: The leadership style of nursing managers influences the quality of nursing care. In contrast, poor nursing methods have significant human and financial consequences. The purpose of this study was to determine nursing managers' leadership styles and assess relevant characteristics from the perspective of nurses.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted in 2019 at Kermanshah Educational Hospitals in western Iran. We recruited 313 nurses using stratified random sampling. Data were collected using a demographic information checklist and the Persian Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire (MLQ).

Results: From the perspective of nurses, nursing managers utilized transformational leadership style quite frequently, transactional leadership style frequently, but not always, and passive/avoidant behavior leadership style occasionally. Nursing managers employed transactional leadership style more than others, as evidenced by the higher mean.

Conclusion: According to the findings, transactional leadership is the most commonly used style in university hospitals, as opposed to other types. Given the critical role of leadership in addressing current and future difficulties, our findings highlight the urgent need to engage in leadership development in various sectors of healthcare.

Keywords: Leadership style, Nursing managers, Nurses, Individual characteristics, Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire, Iran

Introduction

Leadership is an essential component of health care delivery due to its favorable impact on patients, organizations, and health careers (1-3). Nursing leadership is recognized as a significant predictor of workplace empowerment (4). Nursing management and leadership are widely known for their potential involvement in improving nursing environments and working conditions (5). Furthermore, nursing leadership helps to empower nurses while also enhancing nursing care quality (6).

Choosing and implementing a suitable leadership style may help managers motivate people and assist them in achieving organizational goals (7). Leadership style refers to the leader's approach to leading, implementing programmes, and encouraging followers (8). Leadership styles can be defined as using various combinations of abilities, activities, and transaction behaviours to help individuals achieve organizational goals (9,10). Employing leadership styles is an important aspect of leadership skills (5, 11, 12), and nursing leaders typically use a variety of leadership styles to achieve organizational goals. Leadership style is also thought to play an important effect in the quality of care (13). Experienced leaders aim to prevent nurse burnout and improve patient satisfaction by fostering a healthy and supportive work environment, encouraging nurse participation, and implementing transformational leadership (14). Yodang et al.'s systematic study found an underlying favorable link between leadership, patient satisfaction, and patient outcome improvement (15). They also indicated that transformative, honest, and ethical leadership models are more effective at improving patient safety outcomes (15).

According to research, leadership style can have a favorable impact on job satisfaction (12), organisational commitment, and productivity (16). The literature introduces a number of leadership styles. Avolio and Bass' Full Range Leadership Model (FRLM) presents a comprehensive perspective on leadership styles, categorizing them as transformational, transactional, and passive/avoidant (16). The first leadership type, transformational leadership, encourages followers to go above and beyond what is expected of them. This leadership style aims to boost followers' motivation, morale, and ethics (17). A direct link has been found between transformational leadership and supportive work environments (18). The second type of leadership, transactional leadership, focuses on transactions between the leader and the employee, and both are encouraged to meet their needs. The transformational leadership style prioritizes long-term organizational goals and emphasizes change. Transformational leadership frequently produces results that exceed expectations (19,20). According to

the organization's goals, under this type of leadership, the leader's payment of awards is dependent on the follower's performance (21). Transactional leadership involves motivating employees by focusing on their interests and working towards their goals. Transactional leadership frequently produces the intended results (19).

The third leadership type, 'passive-avoidant conduct' leadership, is made up of two parts. 'Management with exceptions (Passive)' implies a lack of leadership (22, 23). Using an unsuitable leadership style can have negative outcomes such as discontent with the job and work environment, lack of job excitement, abandoning the service, and not giving adequate services to clients (24, 30). The impact of leader behaviors on empowering nurses to apply their knowledge and abilities, which can improve job satisfaction and quality of care (2-4,32). It may also minimize the risk of nursing burnout (3,4). These findings highlight the importance of leadership styles in resolving difficulties related to nursing care delivery.(33) Then it is necessary to identify the leadership-related aspects. This will help managers improve organisational performance (36). Evidence establishing nurse leadership styles and determinants in Iran is ambiguous. The goal of this study was to identify the leadership style and the factors that influence it.

Materials and Methods

This research was a cross-sectional study conducted in 2019 at Kermanshah University Hospital. The study sample was drawn from the nursing staff of facilities associated with Kermanshah University Hospital in 2019.

We employed stratified random sampling to pick 313 nursing staff among 1150 nurses working across all hospitals at Kermanshah University of Medical Science. The number of nurses per hospital was determined in proportion to the sample size of nurses and nurse managers in the respective hospitals.

The sample size of 313 people was determined using small population sampling, with a 10% dropout rate and an error rate of $\alpha = 0.05$.

Measurement

A demographic checklist and a Persian version of Bass and Avolio's Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire were used to collect data. The demographic checklist included information such as age, gender, and educational level.

For measuring data on leadership styles, we use the 2004 version of the Multifactor Leadership Questionnaire, which was developed by Bass and Avolio and is a 5-Likert scale score questionnaire. The

psychometric properties of the MLQ have previously been documented in Iran (43–45). Zahedbabolan et al. also observed that the Cronbach's alpha of the MLQ ranged between 0.82 to 0.9 (46). The MLQ includes eight dimensions: transformational leadership (idealized influence attributes, idealized influence behaviors, inspirational motivation, intellectual stimulation, and individual consideration), transactional leadership (Contingent Reward, and Management-by-Exception: Active), and passive/avoidant leadership. MLQ responses ranged from "frequently, if not always" (4) to "fairly often" (3), "sometimes" (2), "once in a while" (1), and "not at all" (0).

Statistical analysis

Data was analyzed using SPSS software (version 24). We defined quantitative and qualitative variables using mean (SD) and frequency, respectively. We used independent t-tests, analysis of variance, and chi square to investigate the association between demographic characteristics and leadership style.

Results

Overall, 313 nurses took part in this study. The mean (SD) age was 32.6 (6.9) years, ranging from 22 to 54. The average (SD) job experience duration was 8.8 (6.7), with a range of 1 to 30. The majority of nurses (69.6%) were women, and 90.4% held a bachelor's degree. Furthermore, 45.7% of them had fewer than 6 years of professional experience (Table 1).

According to the nurses' and supervisors' perspectives, the leaders have used all three of the aforementioned leadership styles. The mean (SD) scores for transactional, transformational, and passive/avoidant leadership styles were 3.67 (0.89), 2.5 (0.74), and 1.9 (0.84), respectively. The highest mean score obtained was for the transactional leadership style, which exceeded the MLQ standard. However, the average score for transformational leadership style was lower than the MLQ standard. Among the transformational style scales, the Idealised Attributes 2.6 (0.84) and Idealised Behaviours 2.3 (0.86) had the greatest and lowest means, respectively. Contingent Reward had the greatest mean (SD) of any transactional style Contingent Reward (2.57 (0.83)).

The mean values for Management-by-Exception for both Active and Passive were greater than the questionnaire's norm rates. These findings show that, from the perspective of nurses, nurse managers use a combination of three leadership styles in department administration; however, the extent to which they adopt transformational leadership style is less than the MLQ norm, whereas transactional and passive/avoidant leadership styles are more prevalent. The leader's mean

effectiveness (2.41 ± 0.59) was lower than the MLQ standard (Table 2 and Figure 1).

Table 3 shows that there was no statistically significant difference in mean scores for leadership style, passive/avoidant leadership, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership based on gender, education, marital status, employment status, and shift ($p > 0.05$). According to the results of the analysis of variance, there was no statistically significant difference in the mean score of leadership style, passive/avoidant leadership, transactional leadership, and transformational leadership based on gender, education, marital status, employment status, and shift ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3).

Discussion

Nurses reported that nursing managers used all three leadership styles: transformational, transactional, and passive/avoidant. A higher score in the transactional leadership style indicated that managers utilized this approach more frequently than the other leadership types, according to the nurses. One explanation can be linked to the nature of the nursing profession, which emphasizes discipline and compliance (47). As a result, the investigation of deviations from the fundamental nursing criteria in this field is conducted more thoroughly and strictly (48). As a result, it appears fair that nursing leaders adopt the transactional leadership style more frequently than the other two leadership types. This conclusion is congruent with the findings of a study by Poels et al., who found that passive/avoidant leadership was more typically utilized in nursing homes, highlighting the need for leadership development to ensure transactional and transformational leadership are not disregarded (49).

We demonstrated that there was no significant association between the primary three leadership styles of nursing managers and nurses' personal and occupational characteristics, such as gender, age, degree of education, marriage status, clinical job experience, etc. These findings are consistent with those of the other investigations (50, 51). In the current study, the majority of nursing managers adopted a transformational leadership approach. The issue could be related to the nature of the healthcare facilities' duties and responsibilities in providing healthcare services. Healthcare facilities are typically bureaucratic, which precludes the application of transformational leadership styles. The difference in leadership style between this study and previous domestic studies could be attributed to changes in the methods used.

Table 1. Characteristics of the study nurses in Kermanshah hospitals

		Nurses	
		Frequency	Percent
Variables		Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	95	30.4
	Female	218	69.6
Education	Bachelor	283	90.4
	Masters	30	9.6
Marital status	Married	171	54.6
	Single	142	45.4
Employment Status	Formal and contractual	155	49.5
	Other (design, contract, company, etc.)	158	50.5
Shift	Fixed	56	17.9
	Rotational	257	82.1
Work experience(year)	<6	143	45.7
	6-10	61	19.5
	>10	109	34.8
Age	<30	145	46.3
	30-40	125	39.3
	40≤	43	13.7

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation of leadership style scales of nursing managers from nurses' point of view

Components	Mean	SD	Interpretation*
Idealised Attributes	2.61	0.84	Fairly often
Idealised Behaviours	2.30	0.86	Sometimes
Inspirational Motivation	2.51	0.79	Fairly often
Intellectual Stimulation	2.58	0.83	Fairly often
Individualized Consideration	2.40	0.88	Sometimes
Combined Scales of Transformational Leadership	2.50	0.74	Fairly often
Contingent Reward	2.57	0.83	Fairly often
Management-by-Exception: Active	2.53	0.69	Fairly often
Management-by-Exception: Passive	2.23	0.64	Sometimes
Combined Scales of Transactional Leadership	3.67	0.89	Frequently, if not always
Passive/avoidant Leadership	1.90	0.84	Sometimes
Mean Leadership Style	2.41	0.59	Fairly often

* Not at all (0-0.8), Once in a while (0.81-1.6), Sometimes (1.61-2.4), Fairly often (2.41-3.2), Frequently, if not always (3.21-4)

Figure 1. MLQ Norm scores leadership style scales of nursing managers from nurses' point of view

Table 3. Comparison of the mean leadership style of nursing managers against selected factors from the perspective of nurses in Kermanshah University Hospital

Variables		Transformational Leadership	Transactional Leadership	Passive/Avoidant Leadership	Leadership Style
		Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Gender	Male	2.3± 0.75	3.5 ±0.86	1.91±0.84	2.3±0.58
	Female	2.5±0.73	3.7±0.89	1.9±0.84	2.4± 0.6
P-value		0.074	0.054	0.991	0.061
Education	Bachelor	2.4±0.74	3.6±0.89	1.9±0.84	2.4±0.59
	Masters	2.5±0.78	3.7±0.88	1.79±1.9	2.4±0.61
P-value		0.614	0.673	0.235	0.5
Marital status	Married	2.5±0.77	3.7±0.95	1.9±0.84	2.4±0.63
	Single	2.4±0.7	3.6±0.8	1.8±0.84	2.3±0.55
P-value		0.056	0.127	0.847	0.056
Employment Status	Formal tenured contract	2.5±0.69	3.7±0.84	1.9±0.85	2.4±0.56
	Other (Temporary contract, company, etc.)	2.4±0.8	3.6±0.93	1.8±0.83	2.3±0.63
P-value		0.895	0.54	0.327	0.779
Shift	Fixed	2.5±0.88	3.6±1.04	1.7±0.9	2.4±0.7
	Rotational	2.4±0.71	3.6±0.85	1.9±0.82	2.4±0.57
P-value		0.249	0.806	0.074	0.548
Work experience(year)	<6	2.5±0.69	3.7±0.84	1.9±0.84	2.4±0.56
	6-10	2.3±0.75	3.5±0.89	1.8±0.86	2.3±0.6
	>10	2.4±0.79	3.6±0.94	1.8±0.82	2.4±0.63
P-value		0.268	0.385	0.926	0.28
Age (year)	<30	2.5±0.68	3.7±0.83	1.9±0.82	2.4±0.56
	30-40	2.4±0.68	3.6±0.97	1.8±0.87	2.3±0.65
	40≤	2.5±0.68	3.6±0.84	1.8±0.81	2.3±0.55
P-value		0.697	0.632	0.679	0.608

Furthermore, differences between our results and international studies could be explained by differences in organisational culture, as certain elements in Kermanshah University Hospital's organisational culture may prevent the implementation of transformational leadership styles. Because transformational leadership has the potential to significantly improve nurse performance (52), it is recommended that the foundation for its adoption and application be established.

The cross-sectional character of this investigation restricts the potential of causal inference. Then, the reported connections should be regarded with caution. We only reported on nursing managers' leadership styles as perceived by nurses. As a result, future research should confirm the validity of nursing managers' reported leadership styles. Another potential cause of information bias is the self-reported nature of acquired data.

Conclusion

According to nurses, nursing supervisors adopted a transactional leadership style more frequently. As a result, it is advised that future studies look at nursing managers' leadership styles from the perspective of head nurses.

Funding: None.

Ethical consideration: This study approved by Kermanshah medical university. Informed consent form signed by all nurses. Ethics code is: 980712.

Acknowledgement: We would like to thanks nurses who participate in our study.

Conflict of interest: None.

Author contributions

NF designed the study, collected the data, analyzed it, interpreted it, wrote the manuscript, and revised it. FK conceived the study, interpreted the data, wrote the manuscript, and revised it. AB conceived the study, collected the data, wrote the manuscript, and revised it. SV designed the study, wrote the manuscript, and revised the manuscript; RB designed the study, wrote the manuscript, and revised the manuscript; and MH designed the study, collected data, analyzed it, and wrote the manuscript.

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